

How Job Satisfaction Shapes Affective Commitment: The Moderating Roles of Innovative Climate and Innovative Behavior in a Government Institution

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ABSTRACT: Public sector organizations face persistent challenges in strengthening employees' affective commitment within rigid bureaucratic structures and increasing demands for innovation. Job satisfaction remains a critical issue, and efforts to promote an innovative climate and innovative behavior do not always translate into stronger emotional attachment to the organization. These conditions highlight the importance of understanding how job satisfaction and innovation-related factors interact in shaping affective commitment. This study examines the effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment, with innovative climate and innovative behavior tested as moderating variables. A quantitative explanatory design was employed using a census survey of 115 civil servants and probationary civil servants at the Regional Office XII of the National Civil Service Agency in Pekanbaru, Indonesia. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Job satisfaction was modeled as a second-order construct reflected by satisfaction with pay, promotion, supervision, coworkers, and the work itself. The results indicate that job satisfaction has a positive and significant direct effect on affective commitment. Innovative climate and innovative behavior also show significant direct effects, but their moderating effects are not supported. Satisfaction with promotion emerges as the most dominant dimension, followed by satisfaction with pay and supervision. Overall, job satisfaction remains the primary antecedent of affective commitment, while innovative climate and innovative behavior act as complementary contributors. These findings highlight the importance of fair career advancement, equitable compensation, and supportive organizational practices.

KEYWORDS: Job Satisfaction, Affective Commitment, Innovative Climate, Innovative Behavior, Public Sector Organization

INTRODUCTION

Public sector organizations are increasingly required to deliver efficient, transparent, and responsive services while adapting to rapid policy changes and ongoing bureaucratic reforms. In many developing countries, public institutions face structural constraints that limit flexibility and innovation, making human resources a critical driver of organizational effectiveness (Creese et al., 2021). In Indonesia, regional offices of central government agencies play a strategic role in implementing national civil service policies, where employee attitudes and commitment are essential to sustaining service quality and institutional performance (Pemerintah Republik Indonesia, 2023). Affective commitment represents an employee's emotional attachment, identification, and involvement with their organization and has been consistently linked to positive work outcomes, including job performance, organizational citizenship behavior, and lower turnover intentions (Moreira et al., 2024). In public sector settings, affective commitment is particularly important because employees are expected not only to comply with formal regulations but also to actively support administrative reform and digital transformation initiatives (Demircioglu, 2021). Conversely, low affective commitment has been associated with reduced engagement, minimal performance compliance, and resistance to organizational change, which may undermine public service effectiveness (Dwiyantri et al., 2022).

Job satisfaction has long been recognized as a key antecedent of affective commitment. Defined as a positive evaluative state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences, job satisfaction reflects employees' emotional responses to various aspects of their work environment (Spector, 2022). Empirical evidence suggests that satisfied employees are more likely to develop strong emotional bonds with their organizations, particularly in public institutions where extrinsic rewards are often limited (Ishola, 2025). However, job satisfaction is increasingly conceptualized as a multidimensional construct rather than a single global attitude, encompassing satisfaction with work itself, supervision, compensation, promotion opportunities, and coworker relationships

(Albrecht et al., 2019). Despite this conceptual advancement, many studies continue to operationalize job satisfaction as a first-order construct, thereby overlooking the differential effects of its underlying dimensions. This methodological limitation restricts a deeper understanding of which facets of job satisfaction are most influential in shaping affective commitment, especially in hierarchical public sector organizations (Ozsoy, 2022). Addressing this gap requires the application of higher-order construct modeling to capture the complex structure of job satisfaction and its relationship with employee commitment.

Beyond individual attitudes, the organizational context in which employees operate also conditions the satisfaction–commitment relationship. Innovative climate, defined as shared perceptions of organizational support for creativity, experimentation, and idea implementation, has emerged as an important organizational resource in both private and public sectors (Ehrhart et al., 2025). Drawing on Organizational Climate Theory, innovative climate reflects how organizational policies and managerial practices signal openness to change and tolerance for risk-taking, which in turn influence employee attitudes and behaviors (Herzallah & Da'as, 2021). Prior research indicates that an innovative climate can enhance employees' psychological well-being, perceived organizational support, and job satisfaction, ultimately strengthening affective commitment (Demircioglu, 2021; You et al., 2022). However, in highly bureaucratic environments, innovative climate may not uniformly strengthen commitment unless employees perceive meaningful opportunities to contribute and experiment (Cho & Song, 2021). This suggests that innovative climate may function not only as a direct antecedent but also as a contextual moderator that shapes how job satisfaction translates into emotional attachment.

At the individual level, innovative behavior represents another critical factor in understanding employee commitment. Innovative behavior involves the generation, promotion, and implementation of novel ideas aimed at improving work processes, services, or outcomes (Amabile, 2018; Lê & Schmid, 2022). Employees who actively engage in innovative behavior often experience a heightened sense of autonomy, competence, and contribution, which may reinforce the emotional benefits derived from job satisfaction (Hashemian et al., 2024). Empirical studies have shown that innovative behavior is positively associated with affective commitment, particularly in organizations undergoing transformation (Vuong et al., 2023). Despite growing attention to innovative climate and innovative behavior, existing studies have largely examined these variables as mediators or direct predictors of organizational outcomes. Limited research has explored their moderating roles in the relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment, particularly in public sector contexts characterized by rigid structures and formalized procedures (Jiang et al., 2023). Moreover, prior research rarely integrates innovative climate and innovative behavior simultaneously within a moderated framework while accounting for the multidimensional nature of job satisfaction.

To address these gaps, the present study examines how job satisfaction shapes affective commitment in a government institution, with innovative climate and innovative behavior conceptualized as moderating variables. Job satisfaction is modeled as a second-order construct to identify the most influential satisfaction dimensions underlying employees' overall evaluations of their work. By adopting this approach, the study offers a more nuanced understanding of when and under what conditions job satisfaction fosters affective commitment in the public sector. The objectives of this study are threefold. First, it investigates the direct effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment. Second, it examines the relative contributions of job satisfaction dimensions using a higher-order construct approach. Third, it analyzes whether innovative climate and innovative behavior strengthen the relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment. By focusing on a public sector organization undergoing bureaucratic and digital transformation, this study contributes to the human resource management literature by integrating attitudinal, contextual, and behavioral perspectives and by providing empirical evidence from a developing country context.

METHODS

This study employed a quantitative explanatory design to examine the effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment, with innovative climate and innovative behavior acting as moderating variables. Data were collected using a cross-sectional survey conducted at the Regional Office XII of the National Civil Service Agency in Pekanbaru, Indonesia. The population consisted of all 115 employees, including civil servants and probationary civil servants, and a census approach was applied to ensure comprehensive coverage of respondents (Sugiyono, 2020). Primary data were obtained through structured questionnaires distributed both directly and online. All measurement items used a five-point *Likert* scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Job satisfaction was specified as a second order construct reflected by five first order dimensions, namely satisfaction with pay, promotion, coworkers, supervision, and the work itself, adapted from Cellucci and DeVries (1978) and Mas'ud (2004). The affective

commitment instrument in this study was measured using 6 (six) items developed by Meyer et al. (1993) and adapted in the research of Odoardi et al. (2019). Innovative climate was measured using sixteen items adapted from Scott and Bruce (1994) and Jaiswal and Dhar (2015), while innovative behavior was measured using six items developed by Scott and Bruce (1994) and adapted by Wang and Meng (2019). Data analysis was conducted using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling with the assistance of SmartPLS 3.2.9. The second order construct of job satisfaction was estimated using the repeated indicator approach (Hair et al., 2017). The measurement model was evaluated through convergent validity using outer loadings and Average Variance Extracted, as well as construct reliability assessed through Composite Reliability and Cronbach’s Alpha. Discriminant validity was examined using the Fornell Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio. The structural model was evaluated by examining path coefficients, coefficients of determination, and predictive relevance, while the significance of direct and moderating effects was assessed through bootstrapping with t statistic values greater than 1.96 and p values below 0.05 (Black & Babin, 2019).

RESULTS

Respondent Profile

This section presents the demographic characteristics of respondents participating in the study, which provides contextual background for interpreting the empirical findings and allows comparison with relevant prior studies. The respondents were employees of the Regional Office XII of the National Civil Service Agency in Pekanbaru, Indonesia.

Table 1. Respondent Profile

Demographic Variable	Category	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	47	40.9
	Female	68	59.1
	Total	115	100
Age	20–30 years	26	22.6
	31–41 years	51	44.3
	42–52 years	30	26.1
	Above 52 years	8	7.0
	Total	115	100
Education Level	Diploma	17	14.8
	Bachelor’s degree	63	54.8
	Master’s degree	35	30.4
	Total	115	100
Length of Service	0–5 years	4	3.5
	6–10 years	22	19.1
	11–15 years	42	36.5
	16–20 years	40	34.8
	More than 20 years	7	6.1
	Total	115	100

Source: Processed data (2026)

The respondents were predominantly female (59.1%), with most participants aged between 31 and 41 years (44.3%). In terms of educational attainment, the majority held a bachelor’s degree (54.8%), followed by a master’s degree (30.4%). Regarding organizational tenure, most respondents had worked for 11–15 years (36.5%) and 16–20 years (34.8%). Overall, the sample

represents employees with productive age, relatively high educational qualifications, and substantial work experience, providing a relevant basis for examining innovative climate, job satisfaction, innovative behavior, and affective commitment.

Measurement Model Assessment (MMA)

The measurement model was assessed to examine the validity and reliability of the research instruments measuring job satisfaction, affective commitment, innovative climate, and innovative behavior. The analysis was conducted using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the assistance of SmartPLS version 3.2.9.

Outer Loadings

Outer loading analysis was carried out to evaluate the convergent validity of each construct. In the initial estimation, several indicators with outer loading values below the recommended threshold of 0.70 were identified and subsequently removed from the model (Black & Babin, 2019). The measurement model was then re-estimated to ensure that all retained indicators met the validity criteria.

Table 2. Loading Factor Values

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Loading	Validity
Job Satisfaction	Pay Satisfaction	KK1	0.788	Valid
		KK2	0.871	Valid
		KK3	0.881	Valid
		KK4	0.746	Valid
	Promotion Satisfaction	KK5	0.807	Valid
		KK6	0.845	Valid
		KK7	0.801	Valid
		KK8	0.844	Valid
	Coworker Satisfaction	KK9	0.756	Valid
		KK11	0.782	Valid
	Supervision Satisfaction	KK13	0.895	Valid
		KK15	0.779	Valid
		KK16	0.831	Valid
		KK17	0.886	Valid
	Work Satisfaction	KK18	0.792	Valid
		KK20	0.769	Valid
KA2		0.833	Valid	
KA3		0.818	Valid	
Affective Commitment	KA4	0.764	Valid	
	KA5	0.808	Valid	
	KA6	0.851	Valid	
	Innovative Climate	II1	0.804	Valid
II2		0.820	Valid	
II3		0.718	Valid	
II4		0.716	Valid	

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Loading	Validity
Innovative Behavior		II7	0.794	Valid
		II8	0.761	Valid
		II9	0.705	Valid
		II11	0.798	Valid
		II12	0.810	Valid
		II13	0.722	Valid
		II14	0.762	Valid
		II15	0.824	Valid
		PI1	0.878	Valid
		PI2	0.877	Valid
		PI4	0.868	Valid
		PI5	0.856	Valid
		PI6	0.879	Valid

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

The results of the second estimation are presented in Table 2. As shown, all indicators exhibit outer loading values exceeding 0.70, indicating satisfactory convergent validity (Black & Babin, 2019). Job Satisfaction, modeled as a second-order construct, is well represented by its five underlying dimensions, with indicator loadings ranging from 0.746 to 0.895. Indicators of Affective Commitment demonstrate strong loadings between 0.764 and 0.851, while Innovative Climate indicators range from 0.705 to 0.824. Similarly, Innovative Behavior shows consistently high outer loading values between 0.856 and 0.879.

Construct Reliability and Validity

Construct reliability and validity were assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE), as presented in Table 3. Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability values above 0.70 indicate satisfactory internal consistency, while AVE values exceeding 0.50 confirm adequate convergent validity (Black & Babin, 2019).

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Affective Commitment	0,874	0,908	0,664
Innovative Behavior	0,921	0,940	0,759
Innovative Climate	0,938	0,946	0,594
Job Satisfaction	0,967	0,970	0,670

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

As shown in Table 3, all constructs demonstrate strong reliability, with Cronbach’s Alpha values ranging from 0.874 to 0.967 and Composite Reliability values between 0.908 and 0.970. These results indicate a high level of internal consistency across all measurement scales. In addition, the AVE values for Affective Commitment, Innovative Behavior, Innovative Climate, and Job Satisfaction range from 0.594 to 0.759, exceeding the recommended minimum threshold of 0.50.

Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity was evaluated using the Fornell–Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait–Monotrait ratio (HTMT), as presented in Tables 4 and 5. According to the Fornell–Larcker criterion, discriminant validity is established when the square root of

the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct is greater than its correlations with other constructs (Henseler et al., 2015). In addition, HTMT values below the conservative threshold of 0.85 indicate adequate discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 4. Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Variable	Affective Commitment	Innovative Behavior	Innovative Climate	Job Satisfaction
Affective Commitment	0,815			
Innovative Behavior	0,618	0,871		
Innovative Climate	0,680	0,714	0,771	
Job Satisfaction	0,585	0,475	0,700	0,818

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

As shown in Table 4, the square root of AVE for each construct, displayed along the diagonal, exceeds the corresponding inter-construct correlations, indicating satisfactory discriminant validity based on the Fornell–Larcker criterion (Henseler et al., 2015). Furthermore, the HTMT values reported in Table 5 range from 0.492 to 0.768, all of which are below the recommended threshold, providing additional support for discriminant validity. Overall, the results confirm that all constructs in the model are empirically distinct and that the measurement model demonstrates adequate discriminant validity, allowing the analysis to proceed to the evaluation of the structural model and hypothesis testing.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT))

Variable	Affective Commitment	Innovative Behavior	Innovative Climate	Job Satisfaction
Affective Commitment				
Innovative Behavior	0,682			
Innovative Climate	0,732	0,768		
Job Satisfaction	0,619	0,492	0,724	

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

Second-Order Construct Assessment

The assessment of the second-order construct was conducted to examine whether the first-order dimensions adequately represent Job Satisfaction as a higher-order construct (Hair et al., 2017). Job satisfaction was modeled as a reflective second-order construct comprising five dimensions, namely satisfaction with pay, promotion, coworkers, supervision, and the work itself.

Table 6 Second-order Construct

Path	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Satisfaction with Pay -> Job Satisfaction	0,260	40,880	0,000
Promotion -> Job Satisfaction	0,271	26,295	0,000
Coworkers -> Job Satisfaction	0,124	18,349	0,000
Supervision -> Job Satisfaction	0,220	21,912	0,000
the Work itself -> Job Satisfaction	0,196	27,792	0,000

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

The results presented in Table 6 indicate that all first-order dimensions exhibit positive and statistically significant loadings on the higher-order construct of job satisfaction ($p < 0.000$), confirming the validity of the hierarchical component model (Hair et al., 2017). Among the dimensions, promotion satisfaction shows the strongest contribution to overall job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.271$),

followed by satisfaction with pay ($\beta = 0.260$) and supervision satisfaction ($\beta = 0.220$). The dimensions of the work itself ($\beta = 0.196$) and coworker satisfaction ($\beta = 0.124$) also demonstrate significant but relatively weaker contributions. These findings suggest that career advancement opportunities, compensation fairness, and supervisory support are the most influential factors shaping job satisfaction among civil servants and probationary civil servants at the Regional Office XII of the National Civil Service Agency. This pattern reflects the characteristics of public sector organizations, where formal career structures, remuneration systems, and leadership practices play a central role in shaping employees' overall job evaluations. While intrinsic aspects of work and interpersonal relationships remain important, their comparatively lower loadings indicate that they contribute less to overall job satisfaction in a bureaucratic and regulation driven institutional context.

Coefficient of Determination (R²) and Predictive Relevance (Q²)

The explanatory power of the structural model was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R²) and predictive relevance (Q²), as presented in Table 7. The R² value indicates the proportion of variance in the endogenous construct explained by its predictors, while the Q² value assesses the model's predictive relevance through the blindfolding procedure (Black & Babin, 2019).

Table 7. R Square and Q Square

Variabel	R Square	Q Square
Affective Commitment	0,533	0,334

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

As shown in Table 7, affective commitment has an R² value of 0.533, indicating that job satisfaction, innovative climate, innovative behavior, and their interaction terms collectively explain 53.3 percent of the variance in affective commitment. This value reflects a moderate to substantial level of explanatory power in the context of behavioral and organizational research. Furthermore, the Q² value for affective commitment is 0.334, which is greater than zero, indicating strong predictive relevance of the structural model. Overall, these results suggest that the proposed model demonstrates adequate explanatory and predictive capability in explaining affective commitment among employees at the Regional Office XII of the National Civil Service Agency in Pekanbaru.

Structural Model Results

The structural model was evaluated to examine the direct effects of job satisfaction, innovative climate, and innovative behavior on affective commitment, as well as the moderating roles of innovative climate and innovative behavior. The results of the path coefficient analysis are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Structural Model Path Coefficients

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Job Satisfaction -> Affective Commitment	0,233	2,582	0,010
Innovative Climate -> Affective Commitment	0,301	2,861	0,004
Innovative Behavior -> Affective Commitment	0,295	3,152	0,002
Moderating Effect 1 -> Affective Commitment	0,057	0,585	0,559
Moderating Effect 2 -> Affective Commitment	-0,123	1,348	0,178

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

The findings indicate that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on affective commitment ($\beta = 0.233, t = 2.582, p = 0.010$), suggesting that employees who experience higher levels of job satisfaction tend to develop stronger emotional attachment to their organization (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Similarly, innovative climate demonstrates a positive and significant influence on affective commitment ($\beta = 0.301, t = 2.861, p = 0.004$), highlighting the importance of organizational support for innovation in fostering employees' emotional bonds (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Innovative behavior also shows a positive and significant effect on affective commitment ($\beta = 0.295, t = 3.152, p = 0.002$), indicating that employees who actively engage in innovative activities are more likely to feel emotionally committed to the organization (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). In contrast, the moderating effect of innovative climate on the relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment is not statistically significant ($\beta = 0.057, t = 0.585, p = 0.559$) (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Likewise, the moderating effect of innovative behavior is also not supported ($\beta = -0.123, t = 1.348, p = 0.178$) (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). These results suggest that while innovative climate and innovative behavior directly enhance affective commitment, they do not significantly strengthen or weaken the effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment.

Figure 2. Structural Model Assessments

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Affective Commitment

The findings demonstrate that job satisfaction exerts a positive and statistically significant effect on affective commitment. This result indicates that employees who evaluate their work experiences positively are more likely to develop stronger emotional attachment to their organization. This relationship is theoretically consistent with Social Exchange Theory, which posits that favorable treatment received from the organization is reciprocated through positive attitudes such as emotional attachment and loyalty (Blau, 2017). When employees perceive that their expectations are fulfilled through supportive working conditions, fair rewards, and clear career opportunities, they tend to respond by strengthening their affective bond with the organization. This finding is also aligned with Affective Events Theory, which explains that repeated positive work experiences generate favorable emotional responses that gradually evolve into enduring work attitudes, including affective commitment (Ghasemy et al., 2020; Robbins & Judge, 2024). Job satisfaction reflects employees' cumulative emotional evaluation of daily work experiences. Therefore, employees

who consistently experience satisfaction at work are more likely to internalize organizational values, identify with organizational goals, and develop a strong sense of belonging. Empirically, the results corroborate prior studies conducted in public sector contexts, which consistently identify job satisfaction as a central antecedent of affective commitment. Gulzar et al. (2020) and Igbomor and Ogbuma (2024) report that employees with higher levels of job satisfaction exhibit stronger emotional attachment and organizational identification. Similar evidence is provided by Matoka and Ngatuni (2023), who demonstrate that job satisfaction significantly predicts affective commitment among public university employees. Collectively, these findings reinforce the robustness of job satisfaction as a key predictor of affective commitment, particularly within bureaucratic and rule-oriented organizational environments.

Dominant Dimensions of Job Satisfaction in the Public Sector Context

A key contribution of this study lies in its examination of job satisfaction as a second-order construct within a public sector context. The results demonstrate that promotion satisfaction constitutes the most influential dimension of overall job satisfaction, followed by satisfaction with pay and supervision. Although satisfaction with coworkers and the work itself remain statistically significant, their relative contributions are weaker. This pattern is consistent with the institutional characteristics of public sector organizations, where formal career structures, administrative hierarchies, and procedural rules strongly shape employees' work evaluations. In government institutions, promotion functions not only as a mechanism for financial advancement but also as a symbol of recognition, professional status, and long-term career security. Consequently, perceptions of fairness and transparency in promotion systems play a central role in shaping overall job satisfaction (Meyer et al., 2021; Robbins & Judge, 2024). The substantial contribution of pay satisfaction further highlights the importance of distributive justice in bureaucratic settings. Although compensation systems in the public sector are typically standardized, employees' perceptions of pay adequacy and fairness remain critical determinants of their job evaluations. Prior studies suggest that perceived equity in compensation is closely associated with positive work attitudes, particularly in organizations characterized by limited performance-based rewards (Demircioglu, 2021; Kim & Beehr, 2022).

Similarly, the significant role of supervision reflects the importance of leadership quality in public organizations. Supervisors act as key representatives of the institution, translating formal rules into daily managerial practices. Supportive and fair supervision has been shown to enhance employees' perceptions of organizational care, thereby strengthening job satisfaction in highly regulated environments (Li et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2024). While intrinsic aspects of work and coworker relationships continue to contribute to job satisfaction, their comparatively weaker influence suggests that structural and procedural factors dominate satisfaction assessments in regulation-driven institutions. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that, in public sector contexts, job satisfaction is more strongly shaped by institutional arrangements and governance mechanisms than by task autonomy alone (Borst et al., 2019; Demircioglu, 2021). Overall, these results underscore the importance of career management systems, compensation fairness, and supervisory practices in enhancing job satisfaction among civil servants. By identifying the dominant dimensions of job satisfaction, this study provides nuanced insight into how public organizations can more effectively foster positive employee attitudes and strengthen affective commitment.

Direct Effects of Innovative Climate and Innovative Behavior

The results also indicate that innovative climate has a positive and statistically significant direct effect on affective commitment. This finding suggests that employees who perceive their organization as supportive of creativity, experimentation, and learning are more likely to develop stronger emotional attachment to the organization. From a Social Exchange Theory perspective, an innovative climate represents a form of organizational support that signals trust and recognition, which employees reciprocate through increased affective commitment (Blau, 2017). This result is consistent with prior empirical studies demonstrating that an innovative climate strengthens emotional attachment by fostering psychological safety and a sense of inclusion (Demircioglu, 2021; Pa'wan & Omar, 2018). When employees believe that their ideas are welcomed and valued, they are more likely to identify with organizational objectives and feel proud to be part of the institution. Similarly, innovative behavior shows a significant positive effect on affective commitment. Employees who actively engage in generating, promoting, and implementing new ideas tend to develop stronger emotional bonds with the organization. This relationship can be explained through both the Job Demands–Resources model and Affective Events Theory. Engaging in innovative behavior enhances employees' feelings of

competence, personal accomplishment, and meaningful contribution, which generate positive emotional experiences that reinforce affective commitment (Demerouti & Bakker, 2023; Ghasemy et al., 2020).

Empirical evidence further supports this relationship. Hamza et al. (2024) and Hashemian et al. (2024) find that employees who perceive their innovative contributions as meaningful and impactful exhibit higher levels of emotional attachment to their organizations. These findings suggest that innovative behavior functions not only as a performance-related outcome but also as an important psychological mechanism that strengthens employees' affective ties. Importantly, the results indicate that innovative climate and innovative behavior operate as independent antecedents of affective commitment rather than as contextual variables that modify the strength of the relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment. This distinction is critical for both theoretical clarity and managerial interpretation.

Non-Significant Moderating Effects

Contrary to the proposed hypotheses, the moderating effects of innovative climate and innovative behavior on the relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment were not supported. This finding indicates that the positive influence of job satisfaction on affective commitment remains relatively stable, regardless of the level of perceived innovative climate or employees' engagement in innovative behavior. One plausible explanation is that job satisfaction represents a comprehensive affective evaluation of employees' overall work experiences, encompassing both structural factors such as pay, promotion, and supervision, as well as psychological aspects related to task fulfillment and interpersonal relationships. Prior research suggests that job satisfaction functions as a proximal and emotionally grounded antecedent of affective commitment, exerting a strong and direct influence that may leave limited explanatory space for interaction effects (Meyer et al., 2021; Robbins & Judge, 2024). When employees are satisfied with their jobs, their emotional attachment to the organization is likely to form consistently, independent of additional contextual or behavioral conditions.

Another explanation can be attributed to the institutional characteristics of public sector organizations. Innovation in government institutions is often constrained by formal regulations, standardized procedures, and relatively risk-averse administrative cultures (Borst et al., 2019; Demircioglu, 2021). Within such environments, innovative climate and innovative behavior may contribute positively to affective commitment through direct mechanisms, such as increased perceived support or meaningfulness, but they may not fundamentally alter the way job satisfaction translates into emotional attachment. In other words, innovation-related factors may enhance commitment on their own, rather than strengthening or weakening the satisfaction-commitment relationship.

Furthermore, the non-significant moderating effects may reflect the dominant role of formal employment conditions in shaping attitudes among civil servants. In highly bureaucratic settings, employees' affective commitment is often grounded in perceptions of fairness, career security, and organizational stability, which are core components of job satisfaction. As a result, the emotional bond formed through job satisfaction may be less contingent on situational innovation-related factors compared to more flexible or performance-driven organizational contexts (Kim & Beehr, 2022). Importantly, the absence of moderation effects does not diminish the relevance of innovative climate or innovative behavior. Instead, it underscores that these constructs operate through additive rather than interactive pathways in the examined institutional context. This finding contributes to a more nuanced understanding of affective commitment formation in public organizations and cautions against assuming that innovation-related variables necessarily function as boundary conditions in satisfaction-based attitudinal models.

Implications for Theory and Practice

From a theoretical perspective, this study makes an important contribution to the literature on organizational behavior by clarifying the distinct and primarily direct roles of job satisfaction, innovative climate, and innovative behavior in shaping affective commitment within a public sector context. The findings reinforce affective commitment theory by confirming job satisfaction as a robust and consistent antecedent of employees' emotional attachment to the organization (Meyer et al., 2021; Meyer & Allen, 1997). Unlike studies that emphasize complex interaction effects, the present results demonstrate that job satisfaction exerts a stable influence on affective commitment even when innovation-related factors are considered simultaneously. Moreover, this study advances innovation research in public organizations by empirically demonstrating that innovative climate and innovative behavior function as independent predictors of affective commitment rather than as moderators. This finding contributes to theoretical clarity by suggesting that innovation-related constructs operate through additive, rather than interactive, mechanisms in bureaucratic

settings. Such evidence supports prior arguments that innovation in the public sector plays a motivational and attitudinal role beyond performance outcomes alone (Borst et al., 2019; Demircioglu, 2021).

The identification of job satisfaction as a second-order construct further enriches theoretical understanding by highlighting the differential importance of its underlying dimensions. The dominance of promotion satisfaction, pay satisfaction, and supervision confirms that structural and procedural factors remain central to attitudinal formation in regulation-driven organizations. This insight refines existing models of job satisfaction by emphasizing the need to account for institutional context when examining employee attitudes in the public sector (Kim & Beehr, 2022). From a practical perspective, the findings offer clear guidance for public sector management. Enhancing affective commitment requires sustained attention to job satisfaction, particularly through transparent promotion systems, equitable compensation structures, and supportive supervisory practices. Given the prominence of promotion satisfaction, public organizations should prioritize clear career pathways and merit-based advancement to strengthen employees' emotional attachment and long-term retention. At the same time, fostering an innovative climate and encouraging innovative behavior remain essential complementary strategies. Organizational policies that promote idea sharing, experimentation, and learning can directly strengthen affective commitment by enhancing employees' sense of relevance and contribution. However, innovation initiatives should be designed as parallel pathways that independently reinforce commitment, rather than as mechanisms intended to amplify the effects of job satisfaction.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional research design restricts the ability to draw causal conclusions regarding the relationships among job satisfaction, innovative climate, innovative behavior, and affective commitment. Future studies are encouraged to employ longitudinal or time-lagged designs to better capture causal dynamics and changes in employee attitudes over time (Podsakoff et al., 2018). Second, the empirical setting is limited to a single government institution, which may constrain the generalizability of the findings. While this focus enhances contextual depth, future research should test the proposed model across different public sector organizations, administrative levels, or national contexts to enhance external validity. Comparative studies between public and private sector organizations may also provide valuable insights into whether the observed relationships are context-specific or universal. Finally, future research could extend the present model by examining additional explanatory mechanisms. Variables such as leadership style, perceived organizational support, or public service motivation may offer deeper understanding of how job satisfaction translates into affective commitment in public organizations. Exploring mediating rather than moderating mechanisms may be particularly fruitful, given the non-significant interaction effects observed in this study.

CONCLUSION

This study provides empirical evidence on the roles of job satisfaction, innovative climate, and innovative behavior in shaping affective commitment within a public sector organization. The results confirm that job satisfaction is the most robust predictor of affective commitment, while innovative climate and innovative behavior exert positive and independent effects. However, their moderating roles are not supported, indicating that the relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment remains stable regardless of innovation-related conditions. A key contribution of this study lies in its assessment of job satisfaction as a second-order construct and the identification of its dominant dimensions. The findings reveal that satisfaction with promotion represents the strongest contributor to overall job satisfaction, followed by satisfaction with pay and supervision. In contrast, satisfaction with coworkers and the work itself, although significant, play a comparatively weaker role. This pattern reflects the institutional characteristics of public sector organizations, where formal career advancement, compensation systems, and supervisory practices strongly shape employees' evaluations and emotional attachment to the organization. Overall, this study enhances the understanding of affective commitment formation in government institutions by clarifying the distinct and direct pathways through which job satisfaction and innovation-related factors operate. By highlighting the prominence of promotion, pay, and supervision as core components of job satisfaction, the findings emphasize the importance of structural and procedural employment factors in fostering sustainable affective commitment among civil servants. These results provide a solid empirical foundation for future research and managerial strategies aimed at strengthening commitment in public sector contexts.

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